

AN INVESTIGATION OF THE RSE-M CRACK CLOSURE PARAMETER F(R) ON A LARGE FERRITIC PWR COMPONENT WITH NEGATIVE R-RATIO INCLUDING WELDING RESIDUAL STRESS

M. P. Nielsen¹

Operation of a civil nuclear PWR facility results in a complex variable loading sequence arising from combined mechanical and thermal loadings, which must be evaluated in conjunction with welding residual stresses. This presents a challenge for FCG assessments at the design stage, with no load history, in support of a safety case for components where gross failure must be shown to be incredible within the design life. Assessment methods for FCG are generally contained within in-service inspection codes e.g. RSE-M, ASME XI. The codified methods were not developed for use at the design stage and can be overly conservative as a result. This study considers the treatment of crack closure in the RSE-M code in the case of a low alloy steel component. The aim is to understand the reasonableness of the approach and if this assessment parameter is a potential source of significant conservatism. The primary focus is the treatment of the start-up/shutdown transients, with a negative R-ratio modified via the inclusion of welding residual stress. The study has been carried out using elastic-plastic cracked-body finite element models with a constant defect size i.e., propagation is not explicitly modelled. Crack growth is inferred by examination of behaviour ahead of the crack-tip and CTOD to determine an effective load range on an un-cracked elastic model to subsequently derive an effective ΔK .

Keywords: fatigue crack growth, PWR, life prediction, mean stress, RSE-M

INTRODUCTION

In UK civil nuclear facilities, fracture mechanics assessments (FMAs) form part of the safety case for components requiring the highest reliability claims, referred to as the high integrity components (HICs). A demonstration via FMA is required to show that a target defect size margin approaching 2 can be achieved for the intended operating life, defined as:

$$DSM = \frac{ELLDS}{QEDS+FCG} \approx 2.0 \quad (1)$$

The large components of the primary circuit in a civil nuclear pressurised water reactor (PWR) are subject to complex variable loading sequences during operation arising from combined mechanical and thermal variations, in addition to welding residual stresses. The definition, and number of occurrences of design loads and transients are also inherently conservative to cover variations of parameters within the design basis envelope and fault schedule.

¹EASL (A Division of Kinectrics) on behalf of EdF Energy UK, Gloucester, GL3 4AE

This study considers the approach for determination of an effective stress intensity factor range, ΔK_{eff} , in fatigue crack growth (FCG) assessments of large thick-walled, low alloy steel, primary circuit components. The aim is to compare a typical codified assessment route for components of a civil nuclear PWR with detailed analysis. The interest here is to consider cases where mean stress and crack closure effects are increased primarily by welding residual stresses which, in the components considered here, give rise to short-range secondary stresses.

The assessment uses parameters from Appendices 5.3 and 5.6 of the French in-service inspection code, RSE-M [1]. However, given that the scope here is concerned with postulated defects at the design stage, rather than those found in-service, there are notable deviations from the basic codified approach which make it somewhat bespoke. These methods for FCG assessments of HICs in the UK were recently reviewed by the UK Technical Advisory Group for Structural Integrity (TAGSI) and reported by Horn et. al. in [2]. The most relevant aspects to the work carried out here are those relating to the determination of cycles from periods of plant operation, referred to as plant operating condition (POC) cycles. However, justification of the POC approach is beyond the scope of this paper, and the reader is directed to [2] for further references.

Appendix 5.6 of [1] defines FCG rate in terms of crack growth per cycle, da/dN . For low alloy steel in a PWR environment the laws (derived using compact test (CT) specimens) are provided in Table 5.6-II.2 depending on sulfur content. However, in all cases da/dN is determined as follows:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C(\Delta K_{eff})^n \tag{2}$$

$$\Delta K_{eff} = f(R)\Delta K_{cp} \tag{3}$$

$$R = \frac{K_{min}}{K_{max}} \tag{4}$$

The general form of the $f(R)$ parameter depends on the magnitude of ΔK_{cp} , sign of K_{min} and the material. The full range of $f(R)$ values for the low alloy material considered here are presented in Figure 1. The expression covering cases where $K_{min} \leq 0$ (negative R-ratio) is given in Equation (5) and is derived from Walker [3]. The exponent in Equation (5) is based on an experimentally determined material constant, $m = 0.75$. This constant, which typically has values between 0 and 1, provides an indication of how strongly the R-ratio affects crack growth rate and can depend on whether the R-ratio is positive or negative. Higher values of m , which are typical of ductile materials, indicate a weaker influence of R on the FCG behaviour. It is also worth noting that the intercept constant C in Equation (2) is defined for $R = 0$.

$$f(R) = \frac{1}{(1-R)^{0.25}} \tag{5}$$

Although not explicitly assessed in the here, for completeness, when $K_{min} \geq 0$ and $\Delta K_{cp} > 40$:

$$f(R) = 1 \tag{6}$$

and, when $K_{min} \geq 0$ and $\Delta K_{cp} \leq 20$:

$$f(R) = \frac{1}{(1-R/2)} \tag{7}$$

FIGURE 1 Variation of RSE-M Crack Closure Parameter, $f(R)$, with R-Ratio for Low Alloy Steels

MODELLING

An axisymmetric model of a cylindrical vessel with $r_i/t_w = 10$, a length of 1 diameter and a 10mm deep circumferential defect has been constructed using ABAQUS finite element software [4]. The component is clad with an austenitic material on the inside surface. Thermal effects of the cladding have been considered, but are conservatively assumed to be non-structural, commensurate with relevant UK practice (defect is considered as surface breaking with crack-face pressure applied). Cladding is not explicitly modelled but is taken into account in the heat transfer analysis via a heat transfer coefficient (HTC) modified using a scaled Biot number according to Chapter VII.2.1.4.3 of Appendix 5.4 in [1]. Sequential heat transfer and stress analyses have been carried out.

A large, constant HTC value has been assumed throughout the analysis. This is representative for normal operating conditions when flow rates are high. Although not the case for some parts of the start-up or shutdown, for the purposes of the study here, the assumption is judged reasonable.

For initial consideration of defect geometry effects, a 3D model has also been generated containing a semi-elliptical surface breaking defect with an aspect ratio of total length to depth, $2c/a = 6/1$, postulated on the inside surface with a circumferential orientation. This is the main type of defect considered at the design stage and is generally the most onerous configuration for a thick section component in which the main loading arises from pressurised cold thermal shock. To confirm the appropriateness of an axisymmetric model for inferring behaviour of the deepest point of a semi-elliptical defect, the elastic stress-strain hysteresis loop 50 μ m ahead of the crack tip from the 3D and axisymmetric models for the 2nd loading cycle are compared in Figure 2. The loading cycle is defined in more detail later in the paper; however, it gives rise to a complex hysteresis loop. These have initially been used only to draw conclusions in terms of defect modelling geometry. It is observed that the strain ranges for both analyses are similar, while the stress range for the axisymmetric case is larger, as expected. The overall trends between the two analyses are judged sufficiently similar such that it is considered acceptable to use the axisymmetric model to form conclusions here. Both models are shown in Figure 3. Further, detailed consideration of the hysteresis loops to infer crack growth is provided later when discussing the elastic-plastic analyses.

FIGURE 2 Comparison of Elastic Stress-Strain Hysteresis for 3D and Axisymmetric Models

FIGURE 3 Finite Element Models used in the Study

The component is assumed to be constructed from low alloy steel, type 16MND5, with austenitic cladding on the inside surface. Elastic tensile and physical properties have been taken from Appendix Z I of RCC-M at 20°C and 300°C. Stress-strain data are taken from Appendix 5.6 of [1]. Due to modelling complexities (size of the analysis and contact), linear kinematic hardening is assumed. The hardening slope has been assumed to envelope the stress-strain data in the low strain region to conservatively underestimate plasticity, which is expected to be beneficial for the geometry and loadings considered here. The stress-strain inputs assumed in the analyses are show in Figure 4.

It should be noted that the aim of the analyses here is not to provide definitive values in terms of damage, but to illustrate trends. The importance of material hardening models and associated uncertainty in finite element applications is noted, though the approach used here is judged to be suitably indicative.

FIGURE 4 Assumed Stress-Strain Behaviour Based on RSE-M Properties

The loading is defined in more detail later. However, to set the logic for the cases considered, the part of the POC cycle analysed in detail is the shutdown/start-up operation. In the components considered here, start-up operations result in heating transients, giving rise to compressive stresses on the internal surface resulting in a negative R-ratio. Consideration of the influence of welding residual stress (WRS) leads to the following cases to be analysed:

1. Negative R-ratio, no WRS.
2. Negative R-ratio, enhanced by low/moderate WRS.
3. Positive R-ratio, due to high WRS.

Case 1 is the base case and representative of assessments carried out on ferritic parent materials. Case 2 is representative of a welded component that has been subject to a furnace post-weld heat treatment (PWHT). Case 3 is representative of loading levels for some ferritic welded components subject to local PWHTs, where the final PWHT residual stress values can still be significant.

WRS are not cyclic but contribute to the mean stress. This is accounted for by a modification to Equation (4), and R-ratios here are determined using Equation (8):

$$R^* = \frac{K_{min} + K_{res}}{K_{max} + K_{res}} \tag{8}$$

The major stress cycles generally occur due to thermal transients associated with normal shutdown and start-up operations. A period of fictitious continuous operation has been defined, which includes an initial start-up, a period of steady operation followed by a shutdown, and then repeated (Figure 5a). The total period considered for one cycle of continuous operation is approximately 54 hours. For analysis purposes, the period of the start-up transient has been optimised to reduce analysis run time. In practice, the temperature is held constant at $\sim 15^{\circ}\text{C}$ for several hours at low pressures while the main coolant pumps are brought into service. This period is omitted from the analyses and the transient is assumed to begin as pumps are started and the pressure is increased, resulting in a rapid temperature change from 15°C to 50°C .

Approximate WRS distributions have been determined from a thermal analysis of an arbitrary cooldown transient, obtained via an elastic thermal analysis on an uncracked model with an undeformed mesh (displacements not written to the ABAQUS *.odb file). The ABAQUS *initial conditions, TYPE=STRESS was used to introduce an initial stress state. A dummy static step was then run to obtain equilibrium to achieve a self-balancing stress distribution with representative values close to the inside surface. This is reasonable on the basis that the scope here relates to small defects in thick section components. Two magnitudes of WRS have been used: “moderate” and “high” representing different PWHTs. The peak values are approximately 25% and 58% of the room temperature (lower bound) yield stress respectively (Figure 5b).

FIGURE 5 Loading Details

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The approach taken for Cases 1 to 3, is summarised as follows:

- Determine ΔK_{eff} , from an un-cracked elastic analysis using $f(R)$ from RSE-M.
- Carry out elastic-plastic cracked-body analysis and use with the un-cracked elastic analysis to estimate ΔK_{eff}^{FE} from the models.
- Compare ΔK_{eff}^{FE} with ΔK_{eff} from the codified elastic route to infer the effect of $f(R)$.

Un-Cracked Elastic Analysis

Combined elastic thermal and pressure stresses at a point 10mm below the surface are shown in Figure 6 from the un-cracked axisymmetric model. Through-wall stress distributions have been extracted at the time of the maximum (shutdown) and minimum (start-up) stresses for an assessment of Cases 1, 2 and 3. K_{max} and K_{min} values have been derived using influence functions for an internal axisymmetric defect from Chapter VII.2.2.3 in Appendix 5.4 of [1] (solution “TUB-CDAI”) to determine ΔK . The R-ratio has been determined using Equation (8) and $f(R)$ using Equations (5) and (6) as appropriate. The results for Cases 1 to 3 are presented in Table 1.

FIGURE 6 Axisymmetric Elastic Stresses from Un-cracked Section (10mm below inside surface)

TABLE 1 Un-Cracked Elastic Assessment Results, Depth a = 10mm

Parameter	Units	Case 1 (No WRS)	Case 2 (low/moderate WRS)	Case 3 (High WRS)
$K_{I\ max}^{tot}$	MPa√m	32.2	From Case 1	
$K_{I\ min}^{tot}$	MPa√m	-32.4		
ΔK_I^{tot}	MPa√m	64.6		
K_I^{res}	MPa√m	0.0	14.2	35.1
R	-	-1.01	-0.39	0.04
$f(R)$	-	0.50	0.72	1.00
ΔK_{eff}	MPa√m	32.3	46.5	64.6

Crack-Body Elastic and Elastic-Plastic Analysis

The effects of prior operating history are difficult to reliably quantify in an industrial engineering application. Nevertheless, an indication of these effects has been studied here by application of a minimum of 4 complete periods of continuous operation, defined as; start-up (no-prior history and hydro-test not accounted for), a period of steady operation (small fluctuations), and shutdown (refer to Figure 5a), followed by a further 3 continuous periods. The 4th cycle is taken to be representative of a stabilised cycle.

It is assumed that FCG only occurs due to energy deposition via reverse cyclic plasticity. For small scale yielding conditions, most of the crack-tip plastic zone is assumed to cycle elastically after first loading (with an assumption that the cycles are roughly of the same magnitude). Therefore, only material where the stresses exceed twice the yield stress is assumed to adsorb energy and contribute to driving crack growth. Practically, the choice of where to extract these stresses is difficult to reliably obtain due to significant stress variations within the process zone. As a practical engineering approach, the time of maximum and minimum elastic-plastic stress, t_{max}^{FE} and t_{min}^{FE} respectively, have been used to determine K_{max}^{FE} and K_{min}^{FE} via the influence function approach using stresses on the un-cracked elastic model. This directly provides an effective load range ΔK_{eff}^{FE} for comparison with ΔK_{eff} determined using the RSE-M parameter, $f(R)$ in Table 1. Elastic-plastic axial (S_{22}) stresses have been extracted 50 μ m ahead of the crack-tip. The distance of 50 μ m was selected to correspond with the characteristic length “d” for low alloy material in RSE-M [1]. Stresses have only been extracted for Case 1. On the basis that the global behaviour of the structure is elastic, ΔK_{eff}^{FE} for Cases 2 and 3 have been determined by simply adding the appropriate value of (elastic) K_{res} , to ΔK_{eff}^{FE} for Case 1. The results are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2 Cracked Assessment Results, Depth a = 10mm

Parameter	Units	Case 1 (No WRS)	Case 2 (low/moderate WRS)	Case 3 (High WRS)
K_{max}^{FE}	MPa $\sqrt{m}$	31.9	From Case 1	
K_{min}^{FE}	MPa $\sqrt{m}$	0.7		
ΔK^{FE}	MPa $\sqrt{m}$	31.2		
K_i^{res}	MPa $\sqrt{m}$	0.0	14.2	35.1
ΔK_{eff}^{FE}	MPa $\sqrt{m}$	31.2	45.4	66.3
$\Delta K_{eff} / \Delta K_{eff}^{FE}$	-	1.03	1.02	0.97

The results from the cracked-body elastic-plastic analyses are within $\pm 3\%$ of the un-cracked elastic analyses, and thus lend support to using Equation (8) to take account of mean stress effects in industrial applications. However, it is noted that the simplified approach taken here does not necessarily provide further insight to why Equation (8) is appropriate, or indeed conservative. Some additional aspects are considered further in remainder of this paper.

An alternative approach to that assumed to obtain results in Table 2 is to determine the elastic-plastic stress range for each case individually and use the respective maximum and minimum times

to determine ΔK_{eff}^{FE} directly¹. To illustrate this, the axial stress-displacement hysteresis loops for the 4th cycle are shown for each case in Figure 7. Stresses are again extracted 50 μ m ahead of the crack-tip, and the displacements are measured 50 μ m behind the crack-tip. There are several interesting features that can be observed from Figure 7:

- In all cases, there is no contact of the crack faces.
- Mean stress effects in Cases 2 and 3 are evident from the vertical shift of the respective loops.
- The minimum stress for Case 1 does not correspond to the minimum opening.
- The additional mean stress in Case 2 results in greater opening range than Case 1, but the range for Cases 2 and 3 are almost identical.

Results obtained by extracting un-cracked elastic through-wall stresses at times t_{max}^{FE} and t_{min}^{FE} and using influence functions for an internal axisymmetric defect from Chapter VII.2.2.3 in Appendix 5.4 of [1] (TUB-CDAI) are provided in Table 3. The results for Cases 1 and 3 remain within $\pm 3\%$ of the un-cracked elastic analyses, however the results for Case 2 show a difference of 10%.

FIGURE 7 Normalised Axial Stress-Displacement Hysteresis Loops

¹ The same concept used earlier applies, that is, the elastic-plastic results are only used to determine time points to extract stresses from the elastic model, on the basis that the elastic-plastic results are very sensitive to the extraction location.

TABLE 3 Alternative Cracked Assessment Results, Depth a = 10mm

Parameter	Units	Case 1 (No WRS)	Case 2 (low/moderate WRS)	Case 3 (High WRS)
K_{max}^{FE}	MPa√m	31.9	32.0	31.9
K_{min}^{FE}	MPa√m	0.7	-19.5	-32.1
ΔK_{eff}^{FE}	MPa√m	31.2	51.5	64.0
$\Delta K_{eff}^{FE} / \Delta K_{eff}^{FE}$	-	1.03	0.90	1.00

A potential explanation to the notable change in Case 2 results is offered by consideration of the positioning of the stress-strain hysteresis loops in Figure 8. Noting that stresses in Figures 7 and 8 are only the component perpendicular to the crack, the different positioning of each loop can be attributed to constraint effects. This is confirmed by calculating the stress triaxiality, η , in Equation (9) taken from Bai et al. [5], plotted as parametrised values, e^{η} in Figures 9 and 10.

$$\eta = \frac{-p}{q} = \frac{1/3(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 + \sigma_3)}{\sigma_{vM}} \quad (9)$$

FIGURE 8 Normalised Axial Stress-Strain Hysteresis Loops

From Figures 9 and 10, in all cases the relative constraint is tending to asymptotic by the 4th cycle, although there is a small increase in the no WRS case between the 3rd and 4th cycle. Despite this the 4th cycle is still sufficiently representative of a stabilised cycle. From Figure 10, the maximum triaxiality occurs for the moderate WRS case (Case 2) during the start-up cycle, when the thermal stresses are at their most compressive. At the same time, there is a significant reduction of triaxiality in the no WRS case (Case 1).

FIGURE 9 Relative Stress Triaxiality for Each Cycle

FIGURE 10 Relative Stress Triaxiality – 4th Cycle

Although of interest, as noted earlier, caution should be exercised when interpreting results from detailed analyses intended to make safety claims on components requiring the highest reliability. It is observed here that potential constraint effects may have a notable impact on the determination of ΔK_{eff} . However, it is conceded that these effects are likely to be due to modelling assumptions, such as, hardening behaviour and the determination of WRS for example. The WRS, approximated by introducing an initial strain field from a thermal analysis, is likely to have a different triaxial state than measured values or indeed that generated via numerical welding simulation. Studies of

constraint effects on FCG of PWR components have not been widely published, though various studies of specimen geometries are readily available, for example, [6] to [9] which suggest constraint effects are influential.

Even for a relatively simple structure, such as the cylinder considered here, modelling behaviour of a crack in 3D is complex. The analysis here uses an axisymmetric defect which removes some complexity associated with opening/closing variations along the crack front. Nevertheless, even when such behaviour is modelled it should be noted that the defect shape remains a conservative idealisation of an actual defect. This approximation of reality should be at the forefront of the mind of any analyst when interpreting modelling results and ideally, should be validated with experimental evidence. However, aside from issues of transferability of small-scale testing results to real components, loading conditions of the large components of a civil PWR primary circuit are difficult to replicate in small scale tests. The actual loading is a combination of primary and secondary loads, in which the latter is dominant. Although not dominant, the primary stresses do have a significant impact on the positioning of the stress-strain hysteresis loop, and thus should not be neglected. The secondary loads are due to through-wall thermal stresses caused by transient temperatures, and as such can be considered short-range and displacement-controlled. Although it is possible to evaluate fracture behaviour using small-scale tests under displacement-controlled loading, such tests are difficult to design when the “displacement” in the real structure is due to thermal expansion, in which the variable temperature field also gives rise to stiffness variations due to changes in Young’s modulus.

Whilst the observations from the detailed analyses are of interest, the uncertainties associated with modelling mean that they are not considered to undermine the findings of the more simplified approach when applied in the context of an industrial structural assessment. Further modelling of different geometries, loading configurations and materials is required in order to draw more unified general conclusions. Nevertheless, the outcome of the detailed analyses does result in the same broad conclusions as the more simplified case i.e. mean stress effects due to short-range secondary WRS result in enhancements to ΔK_{eff} , similar to those derived using codified $f(R)$ parameter.

CONCLUSIONS

An investigation of the RSE-M crack closure parameter, $f(R)$, originally obtained using CT specimens has been performed by comparing with results generated from elastic-plastic cracked body finite element analyses of a structure representative of a large PWR primary circuit component.

Determination of ΔK_{eff} from a model of a cracked structure is highly sensitive to the location used to extract results in terms of proximity to the crack tip. Given this, a simplified approach was adopted here using the time of maximum and minimum elastic-plastic stress $50\mu\text{m}$ ahead of the crack tip to extract stresses from an un-cracked elastic model and ΔK_{eff} obtained using the influence function approach. Similarly, when accounting for the effect of mean stress, a simple addition of the elastic K_{res} was used to raise the mean stress. The basis for this was that residual stress is a global stress field and any relaxation or redistribution at, or near, the crack tip does not impact the global shakedown. Results from these analyses were shown to give good agreement with those obtained using the RSE-M $f(R)$ parameter and provide support to the modified R-ratio, denoted R^* in this paper, to take account of residual stress in structural assessments.

Potential further explanation of the results was undertaken with the aim of providing more insight to the mechanics of $f(R)$. The outcome of this was that there are potential effects of constraint in determination of ΔK_{eff} in the case considered. However, it was also conceded that constraint introduced in the model is dependent on assumptions made; for example, the material hardening

laws, and introduction of the WRS. These factors introduce uncertainties in terms of specific results in very detailed analyses. Nevertheless, the general behaviour observed in terms of enhancement of ΔK_{eff} with increasing mean stress is confirmed. Further modelling is required of a range of geometries, loadings and materials in order to draw more generalised conclusions.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

C	=	Intercept constant on the log-log FCG rate curve
ΔK_{cp}	=	elastic stress intensity factor range with confined plasticity correction
ΔK_{eff}	=	effective stress intensity factor range
$\Delta K_{\text{eff}}^{\text{FE}}$	=	effective stress intensity factor range from finite element model, $K_{\text{max}}^{\text{FE}} - K_{\text{min}}^{\text{FE}}$
d	=	characteristic length for low alloy steel material, taken as 50 μm
ELLDS	=	end-of-life limiting defect size
FCG	=	fatigue crack growth
K_{max}	=	maximum elastic stress intensity factor
K_{min}	=	minimum elastic stress intensity factor
$K_{\text{max}}^{\text{FE}}$	=	stress intensity factor at time of maximum elastic-plastic stress
$K_{\text{min}}^{\text{FE}}$	=	stress intensity factor at time of minimum elastic-plastic stress
n	=	slope of the log-log FCG rate curve (in region II)
QEDS	=	qualified examination defect size
ri	=	internal radius
$t_{\text{max}}^{\text{FE}}$	=	time of maximum elastic-plastic stress
$t_{\text{min}}^{\text{FE}}$	=	time of minimum elastic-plastic stress
t_{w}	=	wall thickness

REFERENCE LIST

- (1) AFCEN, *In-Service Inspection Rules for Mechanical Components of PWR Nuclear Islands*, RSE-M 2018 Edition
- (2) Horn, A.J. et. al., The UK Technical Advisory Group on the Structural Integrity of High Integrity Plant (TAGSI), *A Review of the Fatigue Crack Growth Assessment Approach to Transient Cycles and Some of the Other Parameters Used*, TAGSI/P(23)222, Issue 1, 2024.
- (3) Walker, K., *The Effect of Stress Ratio During Crack Propagation and Fatigue for 2024-T3 and 7075-T6 Aluminium*, Effects of Environment and Complex Load History on Fatigue Life, ASTM STP 462, American Society for Testing and Material, 1970, pp. 1-14.
- (4) Simulia, ABAQUS Version 6.14, 2014.
- (5) Bai, Y., Teng, X., and Wierzbicki, T., *On Application of Stress Triaxiality Formula for Plane Strain Fracture Testing*, Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology, Transactions of the ASME, April 2009, Vol 131.
- (6) Pellereau, B., Currie, C. and Mann, J., *Investigation into Crack Closure Effects for fatigue crack Growth Under Negative R Conditions*, PVP2020-21627, Proceedings of the ASME 2020 Pressure Vessels and Piping Conference, PVP2020, July 19-24, 2020, Minneapolis, Minnesota, USA.
- (7) Watson, C., Currie, C. and Emslie, J., *Accounting for Negative R-Ratio (Crack Closure) in Fatigue Crack growth Calculations on Stainless Steel Components*, PVP2015-45622,

Proceedings of the ASME 2015 Pressure Vessels and Piping Conference, PVP2015, July 19-23, 2020, Boston Massachusetts, USA.

- (8) Varfolomeev, I. Luke, M., and Moroz, S, *Experimental and Numerical Investigations of Fatigue Crack Growth in Various Specimen Geometries*, Fatigue 2010, Procedia Engineering 2 (2010) 1829-1837.
- (9) Xinting, M. et. al. *Effect of Constraint and Crack Contact Closure on Fatigue Crack Mechanical Behaviour of Specimen Under Negative Loading Ratio by Finite Element Method*, Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute, Metals 2022, 12, 1858, <https://doi.org/10.3390/met12111858>.